

Research Software Directories: What, Why and How?

 Jurriaan Spaaks ²

¹ Imperial College London, UK ² Netherlands eScience Center, The Netherlands ³ Stanford University, US

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4430819](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4430819)

Software

- [SORSE](#)
- [Event Website](#)

Category: discussions

Published: August 18, 2020

License

Authors of papers retain copyright and release the work under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License ([CC-BY](#)).

This discussion session will focus on Research Software Directories: catalogues to showcase the software outputs of an institution or community. We will introduce the topic before demonstrating three independently-developed open source directories, explaining their respective benefits and ease of use, deployment and maintenance. Then we intend to form breakout groups to discuss some of the challenges associated with maintaining and curating such directories.

By discussion of these topics with a wider audience we hope to not only promote the benefits of directories and encourage their deployment but also to identify issues and gather ideas to address them. In particular:

- Curation: criteria for inclusion, data quality, scalability, automation
- Federation: scope, data sharing, distributed search, interoperability with other systems and standards
- Technology: platforms, data models, ease of development and maintenance
- Sustainability: direct and indirect costs for deployment and maintenance

The platforms that will be demonstrated and used to encourage discussion are:

- The [Research Software Directory](#) developed by the Netherlands eScience Center
- The [Research Software Encyclopedia](#)
- [GitHub Search](#) as a template for an individual or institution
- Imperial College London's [Research Software Directory](#)